

Novel Secured Architecture with Effective Data Sharing in Cloud Based Big Data Storage Environment

By

Ravi Kanth Motupalli

A Research Report Submitted for the fulfillment

of the award

of

Post-Doctoral Fellow Certificate

Program in

Cloud based Big Data Storage Environment

Under the Supervision of

Dr. Krishna Prasad K, Professor,

Srinivas University, Karnataka, India.

Institute of Engineering and Technology,

Srinivas University, Mukka, Manglore,

(A Statutory University under UGC Act, Govt. of India)

Mangaluru- 574 146, Karanataka, India.

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CERTIFICATES

RESEARCH SUPERVISOR REPORT

This is to certify that the Research Report entitled “Novel secured architecture with effective data sharing in cloud based big data storage environment” submitted to Srinivas University, Karnataka, India by Ravi Kanth Motupalli, for the award of Post-Doctoral Fellow Certificate in Cloud based Big Data Storage Environment is a record of bonafide research work carried out by him under my supervision. The Research Report (consist with the Publications) has reached the standard of regulations for the award, and it has not been previously formed for the award of any qualifications or any other similar title to the candidate or any other person.

Dr. Krishna Prasad K,
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DECLARATION

Declaration

I, Ravi Kanth Motupalli, (Post-Doctoral Fellow Certificate Scholar) hereby declare that the research work presented in this form of Research Report is prepared by me based on my publications (which are never submitted for any qualifications) and all the works have been connected to reach the theme of the topic and its interdisciplinary area. The descriptions and narrations found are purely original and authentic. Moreover, I am responsible for all the contents included in the publications and research report.

Hence, once again I declare that the entire work in this research report is original for the award of Post-Doctoral Fellow Certificate Scholar of Srinivas University, Karnataka, India.

Ravi Kanth Motupalli

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Ravi Kanth Motupalli

DEDICATION

DEDICATED TO ALL HUMAN BEINGS

Paper Publications

List of Paper Publications

The following are the details of Paper Publications in respect of Post- Doctoral Research Fellow Certificate Program in *Cloud based Big Data storage environment* as per the title of the work ‘ *Novel secured architecture with effective data sharing in cloud based big data storage environment*’ in the specified term.

Serial No.	Title of the Paper	Publication Description	Appeared in	Role
1	A Novel Inconsequential Encryption Algorithm for Big Data in Cloud Computing	Journal of Computer Sciences Institute, Vol. 23(2022),140-144.	Journal	Authored
2	Distributed Authentication Using Blockchain for Protected Communication in Cloud Based IoT Platform	International Journal of Management, Technology, and Social Sciences (IJMTS), ISSN: 2581-6012, Vol. 7, No. 2, December 2022	Journal	Authored
3	Augmenting the Cloud Environment Security through Blockchain Based Hash Algorithms	Journal of Computer Sciences Institute, Vol. 26(2023),1-6.	Journal	Authored

Patent Publication

List of Patent Publication

The following is the details of Patent Publication in respect of Post- Doctoral Research Fellow Certificate Program in *Cloud based Big Data Storage Environment* as per the title of the work '*Novel secured architecture with effective data sharing in cloud based big data storage environment*' in the specified term.

Serial No.	Title of the Patent	Patent Filing Details	Published in	Role
1	A System and Method for Secured Architecture with effective Data Sharing in Cloud Based Big Data Storage Environment	Patent Application No: 202241075334 Date of File: 25 th December 2022.	Indian Patent Office (IPO)	Authored

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Research Proposal

RESEARCH PROPOSAL - Post Doc Research Fellow in Computer Science

NAME OF CANDIDATE: Dr. Ravikanth Motupalli

RESEARCH FIELD: Cloud based Big Data Storage Environment

TOPIC OF RESEARCH: Novel secured architecture with effective data sharing in cloud based big data storage environment.

ADVISOR: Dr. Krishna Prasad K

Professor and HoD in Cyber Security and Cyber Forensics, Institute of Engineering and Technology, SrinivasUniversity.

Abstract

Big data security is a challenging task with many complexities. Big data security is mainly dependent on the infrastructure, data type, management, resource allocation and management and Data analysis. Cloud computing is the trending technology dealing with the big data analysis and storage. A novel architecture involving the data outsourcing, data sharing and data management is proposed for the security of the cloud environment in multiple layers. A hybrid algorithmic module was developed for the important procedures like Data compression, Data clustering and Data Indexing. Corresponding attributes were tested for the analysis of the performance metrics. Though many research and studies were done on the cloud security none of them proved the strength and effectiveness of the security architecture. Hence a decentralized security architecture based on the block chain codes was developed for the IoT applications. A special authentication protocol was proposed for this architecture. All these experiments were conducted in a spark environment to demonstrate the effectiveness of the security performance against space complexity, time complexity and throughput.

Keywords- Big Data Security, Cloud Computing, Data Analysis, IoT applications.

INTRODUCTION

Technical advancements have sped up the development of digital information. A study by International Data Corporation (IDC, USA) predicts that by 2025, the digital universe would grow by 400–600 trillion gigabytes of simulated data. The increasing demand for storage and web services, as well as the need for greater storage capabilities and net bandwidth, is a result of the proliferation of alphanumeric data in our world. The increasing popularity of cloud storage-based facilities, particularly those utilizing distant storage schemes, is due to their cost-effective architectures.

The potential to transform traditional computing has made cloud computing one among the most advantageous technologies. The shift in perspective in computing involves a change in the utilization and procurement of computing assets such as infrastructure resources, software, and applications. Cloud storage services generate profits for businesses and government agencies by providing cost-effective solutions and comprehensive analysis of outsourced data. The cloud's pay per use model is contributing to a new era of efficient and effective IT service provision.

Cloud computing offers enticing benefits for both enterprises and end users. The benefits of cloud computing include self-service deployment, flexibility, pay-per-use pricing, workload scalability, and cost-effective relocation.

Security in Cloud Computing

The primary concern for organizations contemplating cloud adoption, particularly in public cloud deployment, is security. The multi-tenant environment of the open cloud allows for the sharing of infrastructure between various customers, as disclosed by the open cloud control. The condition of flooding requests is causing a lack of privacy between congruent process resources. Jannati and Bahrak (2018) assert that accessibility to open shared storage and figure resources is secured by account login credentials in the interim. The availability of private and public cloud features makes hybrid cloud a unique form of cloud computing technique. The increasing need for flexible access to data and information by end users in industries has led to a gradual rise in the adoption of hybrid cloud technology. The hybrid computing environment provides organizations with increased flexibility and improved protection of company data on premises from firewalls, as noted by Lan et al. (2019). The use of hybrid cloud enables organizations to efficiently scale computing resources and avoid significant expenses in managing short-term spikes in demand. The hybrid cloud is a cloud platform that offers the benefits of flexibility, scalability, and cost efficiencies while minimizing the risk of data exposure, making it known as the "best of all possible worlds" cloud platform. Providing facilities and cost-effectiveness to employees and end-users of an organization poses various risks. Achieving the goal of wider hybrid cloud adoption requires addressing key technical security issues.

MOTIVATION

The availability of services in the world is dependent on the essential component of security. The crucial role of data security in cloud network environments. This study discusses the different types of security risks, including application safety, data encryption and key administration, access and identity management, control of physical access, user access control, and audit schedules. Encrypting information and user authentication pose significant safety hazards in a hybrid cloud, as identified by Adam et al. (2016). Providing security to cloud information along with restricting data access can reduce security risks. Ramachandra et al. (2017) assert that the business model of cloud-based services is evolving from basic data storage to encompass crucial online banking, data analytics, and predictive models. The purpose of this study is to propose an efficient data security approach in cloud environments by conducting an extensive investigation of data security models. The goal is to provide the intended benefits of data security and network scalability.

KEY SECURITY CHALLENGES ON CLOUD

Conserving transferred information under unreliable third-party storage poses a significant challenge for cloud-based data access control. This section discusses the challenges involved in implementing outsourced data access control in the cloud using ABE with productive revocation to improve data owner privacy. This paper presents a discussion of open issues in the field, highlighting several key areas that require further research.

Signing and encrypting minimal data: In contemporary times, a growing number of trade and business patrons are required to remotely access their restricted information via lightweight devices from cloud servers. Developing efficient and compact data access control mechanisms that ensure security and privacy is of great importance.

The implementation of a lightweight data access management system that incorporates robust security measures can effectively reduce the computational and storage costs incurred by end-users.

Dynamic Control: The implementation of access control based on Attribute-Based Encryption (ABE) and incorporating user revocation presents a significant challenge. The cost-effectiveness of access control for transferred data in the cloud is contingent upon the implementation of an appropriate and dynamic revocation process. The revocation of a user who possesses a specific attribute is made possible through Attribute-Based Encryption (ABE) revocation mechanisms.

Performance, dependability, and scalability: Performance, dependability, and scalability. Existing methods increase the size of the ciphertext based on the quantity of attributes. Consequently, the effectiveness, dependability, and accessibility of transferred information access control are significant concerns.

METHODOLOGY

The Proposed model utilizes the SALS20 encryption algorithm as an expandable stream of ciphers, with 256 bit keys that correspond to 264 random streams consisting of 64 byte blocks. The input of 320 variables modifies each word in a set of 16 blocks. The addition of the permuted inputs to the initial 64 byte block of the SALS20 algorithm results in a complete 16 bit output. The XOR function of each word in the rotated format with constant distance computationally formulates each permutation. The algorithm's design involves 10 iterations and 2 rounds per iteration. The formulation of each round includes four quarter round pipelines operating simultaneously. A modification of four words is programmed in each quarter round.

The Caesar Cipher Substitution algorithm is a highly effective method for ensuring security in cloud networks. The method involves using numerical secret keys and storing the decrypted cipher text format in a cloud server. The conventional and simplest method of encryption is considered in to be this method. The formation of the cipher text in this encryption technique involves the use of the shift method. The proposed substitutional technique involves double encryption of the dataset to enhance security. The shift value is a crucial numerical value required to generate the cipher text. The encrypted text is generated by moving the alphabets of the cipher exactly "shift" times, based on its numerical value.

The double encryption substitution technique is an effective method for achieving secure user authentication with reduced permutational complexity. The simplicity of this method results in an output that is impervious to cryptanalysis. The proposed substitutional algorithm is more complex than the Caesar algorithm with a double approach in encryption and decryption. The procedure involves multiple keys that must not be mixed up to generate the original data. The substitutional technique is utilized to encrypt the password of each user in the cloud environment, thereby ensuring protected authentication without storing the original password in the cloud server.

The proposed model aims to enhance security across various layers through the implementation of multi-factor authentication. The security of public cloud service providers is dependent on the user's password. The susceptibility of password-based attacks, such as brute-force, dictionary, phishing, etc., poses a significant challenge to the effectiveness of such a system. The thesis aims to enhance the security of financial transactions for public cloud service providers by extending the Honey Encryption (HE) technique, which addresses the aforementioned challenges. This project aims to develop a robust framework capable of withstanding server attacks and unauthorized access.

Block chain technology provides protection against various cyber threats such as DoS, crypto assaults, middle man attack, eavesdropping, hijacking, and password discovery by securing the network. The Elliptical curve cryptography technique is used for encryption and decryption in the suggested paradigm. Extended Parameter-based Honey encryption is utilized for performing the second factor validation in multi-factor authentication. The maintenance of the complete transaction history, including the update timestamp in merkle tree nodes, is accomplished through the block chain network.

ARCHITECTURAL MODEL

Fig.1. Framework proposed for the insignificant encryption algorithm in Big Data

Multiple frameworks comprise the architecture for cloud data storage. In a cloud environment, the proposed framework has four variables named trust center, data transmitter, receiver, and server. The trust center is a robust, robust, and enormous entity designed to ensure the confidentiality of data in the cloud environment. This entity administered the relationship between the receiver, transmitter, and server effectively and efficiently. This entity is also accountable for keeping track of the secret key in all transactions and has the authority to revoke the key if it is abused. Each sender must register with this trust center in order to receive the advantages of secure communication. Similarly, each recipient must register with the reliability center to obtain authorized data access.

ADVANTAGES OF PROPOSED MODEL

1. Security of information is guaranteed.
2. The preservation of user privacy is ensured.
3. The scalability of the method makes it suitable for storing large amounts of data.
4. An external information storing server is unable to access the names of files, contents of files, or any words present within the files.
5. Biometric Authentication is a method of authentication that is utilized.

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A Novel Inconsequential Encryption Algorithm for Big Data in Cloud Computing

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Abstract

In the digitalized era of the information technology the expansion of the data usage is very high accounting for about enormous data transaction in day to day life. Data from different sources like sensors, mobile phones, satellite, social media and networks, logical transaction and ventures, etc add an gigantic pile to the existing stack of data. One of the best way to handle this exponential data production is the Hadoop network. Thus in the current scenario big industries and organizations rely on the Hadoop network for the production of their essential data. Focusing on the data generation and organization, data security one of the most primary important consideration was left unnoticed making data vulnerable to cyber attacks and hacking. Hence this article proposes an effective mixed algorithm concept with the Salsa20 and AES algorithm to enhance the security of the transaction against unauthorised access and validates the quick data transaction with minimal encryption and decryption time. High throughput obtained in this hybrid framework demonstrates the effectiveness of the proposed algorithmic structure over the existing systems.

Key words: Hadoop network ; data security ; cyber-attacks ; hacking ; Salsa20; Advanced Encryption Standard

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1. Introduction

In this digital era the data generated every day for multiple purpose accounts for a very large pile. Data may be of any time from either sensors or devices, Public media or concerns, Cognitive data or transaction data, etc are getting added to the cascading data forming a big torrent called big data. This avalanche of data are the data expansion in the last decade from little to huge volume. As there are enormous amount of data in every information Big data receives its limelight and demonstrated outstanding performance in the field of Digital information technology. These large volume of data can be either in an organized or unorganized format. Uncertainty of the big data is estimated by the organized format of the digital data that is generated in current scenario with the advancement of the novel and modern communication techniques. This is just an initial phase there is a bright future of expansion for the big data in the upcoming decades. The estimated revenue forecast of the big data in US has been illustrated in the Figure 1. This shows the relevance of the big data investment and its progressive expansion.

Big Data is delivered in correspondence with the transmission of data in a broader spectrum accumulated from different sources. Thus Big Data is obligated to set up the data mining computations. The primary requirement of this framework is to assure the security of the data along with its structural analysis. The Information engineering has developed its analysis in an advanced

way migrating from the centralized framework to the distributed framework. In this corresponding study mobile data is taken for the consideration. With the developed gadget usage and the production the amount of storage space in the mobile phones are increased to bigger levels. With high storage device there comes issues with the performance and heat dissipation factors. To avoid such issues and to centralize the storage Big data in cloud storage was introduced to the mobile users. Hence we consider the analysis of the big data stored in the Hadoop Distributed File System (HDFS) [1]. The users of the big data are concerned in gaining more knowledge about the data structure to earn a good profit but fail to consider the security of the data which is the most important attribute of the cognitive communication.

Figure.1. Revenue forecast of Big Data (Satsita , 2021)

Security is an primary factor to be assured in every storage system to save the data from the unfortunate attacks and known hackers. Upon investing it is known that HDFS has no organized security framework to secure the data. Hence the current study intends to propose a inconsequential encryption algorithm to assure the security of the data. HDFS is an distributed network which is built at less expenses with high tolerant against the faults [2]. When enormous data is being used in the HDFS, high throughput is achieved making it qualified to handle the Big Data. The size of the HDFS varies from Giga bytes to Tera Bytes which is facilitated to support the larger files [3]. Thus in a single instance larger data files.

Hadoop is anticipated to handle large amount of data , irrespective of its structure. Hadoop works on the MapReduce structure to handle the index of the web search[4,5]. Hadoop has an inbuilt security framework that makes use of cryptographic technique to mix the data and save it in the cloud. The sensitive data is encrypted to enhance the security where the raw data is transferred in to the cipher text and transformed in to arbitrary data.

The essential intension of this article is to design a technique through which the secure transformation of the data can be done with easy recovery of lost data without increasing the overhead in the computation, communication and storage. Hence in this study an hybrid algorithm mixing AES and Salsa20 algorithm was proposed. In this hybrid algorithm the size of the key is developed up to 256 bits. Apache ranger is used to achieve the cross control over the security of the data. In the proposed work Salsa20 encryption algorithm is executed before moving the HDFS and the data mining computation is done using the mapper class.

2. State of Art

Big Data is a messy, Jumbled and large which has an uncontrollable approach. The accumulated information is segregated and classified to identify the data type in an organized form to be used by a business or an organization[6,7]. Several studies and researches were done to enhance the security of the data stored in the cloud. There are broadly two types of encryption system which was commonly in practise known as symmetric and asymmetric key encryptions[8,9]. Lin.H.Y et al attempted to propose an hybrid encryption system mixing AES and pairing of the HDFS system to improve the security[10]. A novel encryption technique based on the new instruction encryption was proposed by Acharya et al [11] to upright the use of a trusted environment.

Privacy is the term which is used to denote the protected handling and storage of data in the cloud network [12]. Cloud computing has occupied the digital market due to the specialized features like consistency, less expensiveness, rigid against faults and scalability [13,14]. With the suggested usage of symmetric encryption , blowfish encryption algorithm was used in the IOT clod controlling FPGA based devices [15]. Data masking

technique was identified as the simple and efficient security enhancing technique [16]. Hamid et al in his paper highlighted three important key points like security in Big Data, retrieval of information using context aware concepts and ontology integrated big data [17].

Sachin et al had made an conceptual study on the big data security and supported the arguments uplifting the use of high volume data and RDBMS [18]. Bhargavi et al proposed that the original DS is used for the effective use of Big data [19]. The biggest challenge in the Big Data security is the information security , where the data is vulnerable to data leaks, Unauthorized access, DoS attacks, etc. The impression of handling the unstructured enormous data was changed by the Hadoop.

Aditham et al [20] developed an algorithm to detect the attack on the network in two steps. Initially the control of the algorithm was framed in the first step and the process to merge the replicating nodes was developed in the second step. Reddy et al [21] specifically developed detection algorithm for the cloud environment where the access control was the main objective. But this method failed to assure security to the data when providing restricted control over the access. In the proposed framework four stages of the security was ensured. In the initial stage the security for the access control was ensured with the existing technology. In the second or registration process both the receiver and the transmitter were registered to the trust center and service provider to obtain the secret key. In the third stage authentication of the user is validated against the entry of the user with the service provider so as to ensure the access control over the data. In the last phase the secret key of the user is updated or revoked upon the detection of the leakage or misusage.

3. Challenges in the Cloud Storage Security

The data in the cloud is stored in a remote location where the attack or hacking of the cloud environment without proper security features happen, there may be collateral loss of the data assets and information. The physical damage to the cloud server machines may result in unrecoverable data loss. In order to assure the data security the information is replicated and stored in different location where it should be managed effectively to avoid the confusion and data replication issues to the end users. Though the cloud servers are handled by the third entity the service provider themselves should have restricted access to the data to ensure the privacy of the data stored. Hence in order to assure the data privacy through limiting the data access to the service providers, all the data hiding and recovery process of encryption, decryption and scrambling are given to the user side. The security and privacy of the data in big data are considered to be the two giant attributes of its performance analysis

4. Research Methods

The architecture for storing data in cloud has several framework. The proposed framework has four parameters named as trust center, data transmitter, receiver and

server in cloud environment. Trust center is an sturdy, vigorous, and enormous entity that is framed for the assurance of security of data in the cloud environment. The relation between the receiver, transmitter and the server was effectively and efficiently managed by this entity. This entity is also responsible for tracking the secret key in all the transaction and has powers to revoke the key when misused. Each transmitter should register themselves in this trust center to obtain the benefits of secure communication. Similarly each receiver should register in to the trust center to obtain authenticated access to the data.

Figure 2: Proposed framework for the inconsequential encryption algorithm in Big Data

Processes like slicing, transformation of data, encryption, decryption, scrambling and unscrambling, consolidation, and recovery are the basic processes involved in any data transfer. Using an effective secret key the transmitter uploads or stores data in the cloud. When transferring the data raw information is scrambled and converted in to cipher text. Then the cipher text is decrypted and unscrambled at the other end using the secret key provided by the owner to recover the original data at the receiver end.

The process flowchart is illustrated in the Figure 3. Salsa20 algorithm is an efficient stream cipher which can effective transform key bits from 256 to 264 streams

with occasionally susceptible 64 byte blocks per stream. This 64 byte block was represented in 16 word format which is obtained as a result of 320 reversible alterations, one word for each modification [22,23]. The corresponding output was amended to the producing 64 byte output. In each change, two words, one original word and the rotated version of the other was xor-ed twice. Thus each round is performed as 4 parallel quarter rounds.

There is separate function for each quarter round. There is row round function for each quarter which modifies the rows. Then column round function is processed changing the column. Then a double round function is performed for the specified number[24,25]. In this article 20 rounds of Salsa 20 algorithm was proposed. Then the resulting 64byte is transformed in to 16 word format using little endian method.

Thus a 64byte output is obtained. Encryption tools along with the authentication and platform manager was used to improvise the Hadoop security. In this proposed module 10 rounds of Hadoop clustering with specified configuration was done. Deployment validation is highly prioritized based on the running concerns and the Apache ranger is given steady administration platform to configure and strategize the secured data in each cluster[26,27]. The ranger key management service is used for the implementation of HDFS encryption. Apache officer is used for the authenticated data access through the centralized fine grain approval system [28].

Figure.3: Proposed framework flowchart

5. Results and Discussion

For the experimental procedure 10 cluster was created where the first 8 nodes serve as MapReduce clients and as Data Node servers. The last two nodes function as MapReduce scheduler and Name Node manager. The first eight nodes are a 8V processor operating with 8GB random access memory with Ethernet NIC. The last two nodes are 16 V processor with 32GB memory. Hadoop replica was not allowed in this system. The sequenced process of encryption and decryption of enormous data pushes and stacks them into a HDFS.

The encryption time was calculated in milli seconds. To make the system more responsive and more dynamic the execution period should be small enough. Similarly, decryption time should be less enough to accelerate the system. The third important parameter for consideration is Avalanche effect where a small change in the input has big and drastic effect at the output. The encryption time analysis of the proposed system with other encryption and decryption techniques was shown in the Figure.4. This illustrates that the proposed methodology is more suitable for the foresaid applications.

From the Figure 4, it is evident that the encryption and decryption time of the proposed model is short enough to support the processing of big data files quickly and actively. The throughput of the decryption process is observed to higher than that of the encryption process. The throughput is calculated as the ratio of plain text to the encryption time in milli seconds.

Figure 4: Comparison of encryption and decryption time for different algorithms

Performance analysis was done with the other encryption algorithms like AES and blowfish algorithm. From the result it is evident that the proposed technique has higher encryption than that of the other prevailing techniques. Due to the smaller key size the throughput of the blowfish algorithm was very less. The security of the data in the proposed model is measured with the parameter called avalanche effect. A small change in the input stream causing a big impact on the output stream is called avalanche effect. This method allows the data scrambling in a reversible format to enhance the security of the data. Thus the overall performance of the proposed Salsa20 hybrid algorithm is found to have minimal running time, increased throughput, with the augmented avalanche effect guarantying the security of the stacked data in HDFS.

6. Conclusion

The overall concept of the proposed framework is to secure the data transaction in the cloud system through an effective encryption algorithm in the Hadoop network. In this proposed model Salsa20 hybrid algorithm was used for effective encryption and efficient key management. The overall performance efficiency of the proposed hybrid

algorithm is accessed based on the speed of transmission and the less computational time for multiple nodes in a cluster. Thus the proposed framework is guaranteed for the authenticated data access, confidential data storage and controlled access of the Hadoop network. The low computational time and the improvised throughput facilitated the immediate transaction of the data with utmost security. This study is majorly focused on the mobile data transaction to the cloud storage. The future work may include designing framework for the most complicated IoT transaction like defence data storage in the cognitive cloud, Big Data accessing in the educational domain and the large database secured in the healthcare sector.

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ABSTRACT

Purpose: *The technology has improvised to control the devices from the remote location using the IoT framework. To improvise the storage efficiency of the technology the IoT is integrated with the cloud network. When the huge size of the data is generated this cloud server hosts the space for the big data. But the secure exchange of the data between the IoT data is not efficient to protect the confidentiality of the data. The existing security systems are either concentrating on the authentication or secure validation. Hence there is a demand for the lightweight, less complex, and strong secure framework.*

Design/ Methodology/Approach: *The authentication phase of the proposed framework is designed using distributed block chain protocol to authenticate multiple users in the cloud environment. The SALSA20 encryption algorithm which augments the strength of the data security. The protected key exchange is done using the ReDH algorithm. Indexing is done using the hash algorithm to obtain the accuracy in the search results and to minimize the encrypting and decrypting time.*

Findings/ Results: *The proposed distributed block chain authentication framework is proved to be efficient with less encrypting and decrypting periods of about 0.25ms and 0.2ms respectively. 97.5% of the storage efficiency proves this model to be suitable for the cloud application.*

Originality/Value: *The proposed model has a dedicated database for the registration for the users and IoT devices which is used to validate the authentication of the system. The encryption is done using the SALSA20 algorithm and sensitivity level prediction process to measure the sensitivity score.*

Paper Type: *Experimental Research*

Keywords: Block chain codes, Cloud environment, IoT devices, SALSA20 encryption, Hash function, ReDH algorithm.

1. INTRODUCTION :

Internet of Things (IoT) is an evolving and thriving technology that authorizes data sharing across numerous small devices where the input is limited to access [1]. This technology has reached its peak through exponential growth in the past two decades. It was stated that around the year 2019 there was about 7600 million active IoT devices which is estimated to grow up to 24 billion in the next decade [2]. The growth rate of this technology is approximated to about 11% per annum. The growth of the IoT in the past two decades was illustrated in the Fig.1, where it is very clear that each year the number of IoT installations increases exponentially and drastically. The sudden growth of the IoT usage was happened in the year 2010 due to the evolution of the sensors at the very cheap cost where the sensors was used almost in all the networking applications.

The Internet of Things (IoT) Units Installed Base By Category 2014 to 2020 (in billions of units)

Fig. 1: Growth of IoT in the past two decades (Source: Forbes, 2018) [3]

IoT has its presence in many important applications as explained as follows. Wearable sensors is an extraordinary technology that was helpful in monitoring and tracking the health records of the patients from remote location. Smart city IoT is a contemporary application where the renovation, growth and maintenance of the city is tracked and executed through the devices connected to internet. IoT application in the smart home is an innovative feature that controls household gadgets and devices through sensors.

IoT devices are also used in agricultural applications to predict the climate, controlling the motor pumps and water outlets through devices connected through internet. Thus, through the sensors and the devices connected through the internet are used in many other applications like a retail business, tracking and monitoring systems, Industrial applications, etc [4].

Big Data from these IoT devices helps in the data refining, assessing and storage of the data [5]. When the analysis of the Big data is done enormous amount of space is required for the storage of the processed data. This flexibility of the expanding data storage during the analysis of the big data is resolved by the cloud computation [6]. Cloud computing simplifies the accessibility and authentication of data through remote devices [7]. This phenomenon influenced the researchers to develop an integrated authentication model for the secure data communication [8]. The generic IoT network framework is shown in the Fig.2. From the figure it is observed that the resource constrained devices are in the remote location and the server controlling the devices is in the cloud. Both are connected through the Internet.

Fig. 2: Generic IoT Framework (Source: Author)

The end devices are used to interact with the required remote environment, IoT Gateway is used to collect the information and exchanges with the cloud server. An IoT gateway is a centralized hub that connects IoT devices and sensors to cloud-based computing and data processing. Modern IoT gateways often allow bidirectional data flow between the cloud and IoT devices. The cloud server uses cloud

computation to analyze and process the collected information. A cloud server is a pooled, centralized server resource that is hosted and delivered over a network—typically the Internet—and accessed on demand by multiple users. Cloud servers can perform all the same functions of a traditional physical server, delivering processing power, storage, and applications. This simplifies and solves the issue of giant data storage requirement of the Big data. Though this integrated framework has many benefits, the security of the data exchange is still a weak structure. When handling the enormous data exchange, excellent security is a most demanded attribute to assure the safe transaction of the data [9].

2. LITERATURE REVIEW :

The framework of the cloud and IoT integrated structure was illustrated in the Fig.3. With the development of different networks and communication technologies the security of data sharing has become an explicitly significant factor in every communication [10]. Though there were numerous advantages in the IoT technologies, this also has some challenging issues like security and privacy [11]. These issues were considered as the significant and important attributes in the IoT communication. In recent days remote medical consultation through the modern gadgets and technologies has been very common and more helpful in the pandemic chaos [12]. This technology has many benefits including reduced medical expenses and improved quality of service [13]. But the patient’s details are required to be very confidential despite of the consultation platform.

Fig. 3: Cloud integrated IoT Framework [14]

Though the IoT has its successful establishment in other sectors it is highly unlikely in Industrial application due to its security issues. This can be easily explained with the Philips-Hue attack [15]. In this attack in a smart city application, remotely programmed Light sources were re-programmed to turn on simultaneously causing a hike in the energy consumption leading turning off all the lights leaving the entire city in darkness. This illustrates the collapse is caused due to the poor security of the IoT network. This concerned the researchers to develop a safe model for the effective and protected communication in the IoT framework. The effective protected communication should be developed without compromising the quality of service. The requirement is to develop a framework to accomplish the privacy, probity, and the availability of the IoT service with advanced tools and security protocols.

Table 1: Literature survey on cloud security model

	Focus/ Constructs	Reference
Literature survey on cloud security model	An online authentication framework was proposed, where the online finger prints are used to secure the private data. The online fingerprint was recognisable by different servers to authenticate from multiple servers. But this method failed to avail strong security to preserve the confidential data than the actual bio metric data. As the online finger print can be duplicated easily this is an inefficient framework.	Zhu H, et al (2019). [16]
	To overcome the inefficiency in the Zhu et al proposal, an integrated security framework was suggested to combine the user ID and password. Fuzzy extractor is used to authenticate the user through Elgamal algorithm. The algorithm encrypts the user detail and the fuzzy extractor is used to obtain the online fingerprint details. As this framework has increased computational complexity this is not efficient for the Cloud-IoT applications	Maitra, T et al (2019). [17]
	A lightweight protocol using a smart card technique was developed. The major pitfall in this technique is that when the smart card is lost the security is not guaranteed.	Zhou L, et al (2019). [18]
	A block chain code-based security structure was proposed for information exchange with excellent hidden policy. But yet the authentication control in poor and is computationally complex.	Hao J, et al (2019) [19]
	The protected data recovery was done by indexing and key transaction protocols. In the data recovery phase the encryption was done through dual encryption technique. The keywords in the encrypted data were authenticated through fine grain encryption technique. The data encryption was done through AES protocol	An X, et al (2016). [20]
	A Retrieval Feature (RF) tree algorithm was proposed in the data recovery phase. In order to augment the indexing efficiency, RF tree was constructed. This tree was constructed based on a iteration protocol. Hence the searching period was extended due to repeated iteration.	Fu JS et al (2018). [21]
	Parameter based light weight decrypting protocol was developed for multiple servers.	Long J, et al (2019). [22]
	A three-factor authentication system was proposed, later which was discovered for a pitfall of decreased privacy.	Banerjee S, et al (2019). [23]

2.1. Security Challenges in the Cloud Integrated IOT Framework:

The challenges faced during the development of the security model are listed as follows.

- When the security provisioning is done centrally the vulnerability of the server is increased leading to the weakest network which can be hacked easily by tapping a single server.
- As the cloud can be able to accommodate a number of users simultaneously it is un-scalable and vast. But the existing security mechanisms are constrained with the resources and number of users. Hence a secured protocol irrespective of the number of users should be developed.
- With the analysis of huge data high power is consumed leading to the reduced performance characteristics. Hence a rapid and light weight security protocol should be developed to augment the performance of the system.

Thus, from the literature survey listed in the Table.1, it is clear that there is demand for novel secure mechanisms for cloud integrated IoT framework. The D-Block Security framework proposed in this study confides all the three phases like authentication, encryption, and decryption in a protected manner. Verification of the user and the end IoT devices is done to assure the efficient security of the information exchange. Only authorized users are able to recover and decrypt the encrypted data. The framework of the proposed architecture is explained in the following sections.

3. OBJECTIVES :

In order to develop an effective light weight protocol with improvised performance efficiency distributed authentication is used in combination along with the block chain codes. In this research distributed block security (DBlock Security) Scheme is proposed which has command over the protection, verification, encryption, and decryption of the data. The objective of this study is listed as follows,

- (1) Analyzing the existing model of the loud security network and identifying the challenges in the model.
- (2) To develop a distributed lightweight framework with augmented performance efficiency.
- (3) Reducing or minimizing the data leakage in the data exchange system through an efficient protocol.

4. PROPOSED D-BLOCK SECURITY FRAMEWORK :

The proposed phase model of the Distributed block security framework is illustrated in the Fig.4.

Fig. 4: Block diagram of Distributed block security framework (Source: Author)

The end IoT devices are the source for the generation of huge amount of information that is exchanged over the network. This information has to be stored in the cloud environment which is integrated with the spark technology to facilitate the large amount of data storage in the cloud servers. The proposed model confines to three different phases like verification, data encryption and data recovery. The primary concern of the proposed framework is to provide a strong security model for the data exchange between IoT devices and the cloud servers.

The first stage of the D-Block model is the verification of the End IoT devices. A novel database model is developed to verify both the user and the devices. For this purpose, the details has to be registered with the database. This process was a distributed and less complex process simplifying the complexity of the operation. Streebog hash algorithm is used for the registration of the details. These details are stored using the blockchain codes which augments the security level of the framework. The hash algorithm is used to produce the random hash values as the compression function. This is authenticated for the verification of the registered user and the end device and to block the unauthenticated users and devices. The second stage of the framework involves the encryption of the data. Salsa20 encryption algorithm is used for effective encryption in both rapid and simple manner. During encryption the data is divided into blocks and encrypted. For this the sensitivity of the data is measured to obtain sensitivity score. With the improved speed the optimal amount of energy is used thereby reducing the excessive power consumption for the huge amount of data.

The third phase of the framework involves the data recovery. The data recovery is done by indexing and searching. Through these methods the data is recovered in the form of cipher text. Then the ReDh decryption algorithm is used for the data retrieval through a protected key exchange. The entire process is simulated using the Python simulator. Cloud network is set through Apache Spark 2.2.0. After configuring the required hardware the experiment is done. The data generated from the IoT devices are stored in the hadoop blocks. The proposed model is qualified for the big data applications. The encryption is done in the block chain codes ratehr than the servers so as to assure the security for the hidden key exchange.

5. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY :

In the Proposed model the encryption algorithm SALSA20 is considered as a expandable stream of ciphers, where the 256 bit keys of the ciphers are identified with 264 random streams with 64bytes

blocks. These blocks are separated as 16 words which are inputted with 320 variables where each variable is modified with one word. The permuted inputs are then formed into a complete 16 bit output which is added to the original 64 byte block of the SALSA20 algorithm. Thus each permutation is computationally formulated as the XOR function of each word in the rotated format with constant distance. The algorithm is designed to iterate up to 10 times with a series of 2 rounds. Each round is formulated to have 4 quarter round pipelines simultaneously. Thus in each quarter round modification of 4 words is programmed. The mathematical formulation of the SALSA20 algorithm is explained as follows,

Step 1: Initiate the encryption

Step 2: Set second order low level function for 10 double rounds

Step 3: Two 4 byte words are selected and the function $S = x+y |2^{32}|$ is performed

Step 4: Then X (xor) Y is done where bit by bit comparison is performed.

Step 5: Now the leftward rotation is done using the function $2^x S |2^{32}-1|$

Step 6: Then the quarter round modification is done which is a reversible function

Step 7: Finally rowround function is performed and the resulting 16 words are given to square matrix.

Step 8: End the encryption

6. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION :

The results from the proposed model are then compared against the other models like Block AES [24], ABE [25] and Inverted Index[26] framework. The other frameworks consider either authentication process or secure validation, whereas the proposed model is designed based on both attributes.

6.1. Encryption Time:

The time required for encrypting the data is considered to be the most important analysis parameter. This attribute is decided based on the size of the data and the key. The size of the data directly represents the amount of information generated from the IoT devices. The amount of time taken by each algorithm for the encryption of the original data into cipher texts are 20.20ms, 25.85ms, and 0.25ms for the Block AES, ABE and D-Block algorithms respectively. From the results it is clear that the proposed model has minimal encryption time thereby reducing the time and computational complexity of the framework. The comparative analysis of the time taken to encrypt using different framework is shown in the Fig. 5.

Fig. 5: Comparative Analysis of the Encryption time (Source: Author)

6.2. Decryption Time

The time required to decrypt the cipher text into original data is termed as the decryption time. Similar to encryption decryption also processed in blocks and is done simultaneously so as to decrease the time complexity of the framework. The obtained decryption time for the proposed algorithm, Block AES and ABE algorithms are 0.2 ms, 18ms and 23ms respectively. The graphical representation of the obtained data is given in the Fig.6. From the results it is evident that the proposed algorithm has less decryption time thereby increasing the performance of the proposed algorithm.

Fig. 6: Comparative Analysis of the Decryption time (Source: Author)

6.3. Storage

The storage efficiency of the proposed model is improvised when combined with the cloud computation. The storage efficiency in the proposed model is about 97.5%, where almost all the data is analyzed without any error or deviation. The indexing was accurate up to 98% which makes the search easier for the data retrieval. Where the storage efficiency for the Block AES and ABE was 50% and 60% respectively. Thus from the results it is declared that the proposed model is suitable for big data integrated with the cloud technology.

7. CONCLUSION :

Thus, from the obtained results it is very clear that the proposed model is not only simple and less complex but also efficient in securing the information exchange between the IoT devices in the cloud environment. The cloud environment is integrated with the spark, which makes it suitable for the limited resource framework. The developed framework augments the security by validating the registered user in the dedicated database. This framework is flexible and is less complex. The future work of this study may be scheduled to analyse the steps to verify the user profile during registration to further improve the efficiency of the designed framework.

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Augmenting The Cloud Environment Security Through Blockchain Based Hash Algorithms

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Abstract

Many techniques and algorithms are developed to enhance the security in the cloud environment. This helps the users to secure their server from malicious attacks. Hence the study and investigation of the performance enhanced security algorithms is a must demanded field in the research industry. When large number users using same server to store their information in cloud environment security is a must needed component to preserve the privacy and confidentiality of every individual user. This can be further strengthened by detecting the attacks in earlier stages and taking counter-measure to prevent the attack. Thus securing the data network without any leakage and loss of the information is a challenging task in the cloud environment. When the attacks or intrusion is detected after the occurrence there may be damage to the data in the form of data damage or theft. Hence it is necessary to predict and detect the attacks before the occurrence to protect the privacy and confidentiality of the user information.

Keywords: Cloud security; Data privacy; Data confidentiality; Hash Algorithm; Substitutional encryption

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1. Introduction

The most preferred technology for the storage of large volumes of data with data privacy and confidentiality is cloud computing. The security risk in the cloud technology may cause collateral damage to the business applications and the numerous number of users. Hence there are many important security policies in the cloud applications like never leaving the cloud server open for other user which may attract the intruders to steal the data, all the security upgrades given by the vendors should be switched in time to prevent risking the data, Basic cyber security steps should be followed to protect the data from user side, use of strong password and efficient password management, Backing up the data to avoid data loss, should not modify the vendor provided permissions, etc.

When a network is designed to protect the user data or host large numbers of users simultaneously, its ability and competence to serve the users is deprived to have an extraordinary approach to its users. Fig.1 illustrates how the cloud environment protects the end user data against the threats and attacks.

It is the responsibility of the cloud service provider to ensure the authentication of the data access through physical path audit controls and the data protection assurance through the strong security algorithms [1].

The data repositories should be consistently watched for their activities and suspicious behaviours. When the service provider provides more services for multiple users there may arise situations where the details about the users will be backed up in the compatible server. During this case it is possible for any user to duplicate the identity of another user [2]. To avoid such damage to the user data two security algorithms using substitution approach and hash algorithm were devised in this study.

Figure 1: Authentication in Cloud environment.

2. Literature Survey

Many researchers had contributed their study in the cloud security domain. Cloud security involves the confidentiality of the user data and authentication to the user id. It also ensures safety against any type of attacks. Depending upon the applications many type of security algorithms were proposed by different authors and hybrid model of these algorithms were built [3]. Table 1. explains some of the literature work done by different authors on different security algorithm.

When there is any security breach in the cloud server the corresponding counter action should be taken to compensate the attack [4]. Encrypting the original data before transmission is a preferable choice to avoid the theft or data leak. Hence the service distributor should provide a strong security for the authenticated access of the data [5]. Double encrypted algorithm is the advanced version of the authentication algorithm to improve the secure access [6].

Cloud security assures the susceptible cloud server against any type of attacks and intrusions that leads to the malicious attacks [7]. Hence it is responsibility of the service provider to ensure the secure authentication to the data access and assuring the data confidentiality of the user data. This model proposes a hybrid model of substitution algorithm to provide authenticated access and hash algorithm to protect the data confidentiality and avoid data loss or damage.

Blowfish algorithm is a 64 bit block cipher algorithm known to be strong against any type of attacks. This algorithm was not patented and is owned by anyone to use in their application.	Yassein et al, 2017 ^[14] ; Bhuvaneshwaran et al, 2019 ^[15] .
Homomorphic algorithms make use of two different public and private symmetric keys. Losing any one key may cause loss data in decryption.	Yahyaoui et al, 2018 ^[16] .
RSA algorithm is also a symmetric key algorithm which generates two large prime numbers which are multiplied to produce private and public keys.	Mahmood et al, 2018 ^[17] . Gayatri et al, 2020 ^[18] .

Table 1: Literature study on Security algorithms

Focus/ Constructs	Reference
DES algorithm is the first devised algorithm for encryption. But due to weak cipher this is prone to many attacks	Hui et al, 2019 ^[8] ; Srisakthi et al, 2020 ^[9] .
The new AES algorithm was devised to tackle the brute force attacks.	Namasudra et al, 2020 ^[10] .
AES algorithm is simple and rapid.	Sivakumar et al, 2019 ^[11] .
TDES algorithm is the customized version of the DES for triple protection. But the complexity of this algorithm makes it impossible to implement for larger data.	Gowtham et al, 2021 ^[12] ; Kumar et al, 2017 ^[13] .

2.1. SECURITY CHALLENGES IN CLOUD COMPUTING

In cloud servers many users are being served with different services. Hence there arises many different issues in the security of the cloud server and user data. Data issue is considered as the foremost issue where the service provider is responsible for the confidentiality of the user data in the server [19]. Data audit should be conducted through automated algorithms to ensure the confidentiality of the data by avoiding data breach and data corruption.

Privacy of data is another issue in the cloud servers. More number of users being served at the same instance there is a chance of a data backlog that leads to the cross access of another user's data. In order to avoid this data breach and to maintain data privacy each user access should be verified using a two way authentication approach [20].

Security issue is a must addressable issue that avoids data tampering and data theft. The cloud server should not be vulnerable to the external attacks and must ensure to detect the data attack at the early stage and avoid data damage or loss [21].

3. Objectives

The main objective of this research is to find an effective security algorithm to protect the data confidentiality and privacy of every individual user in the cloud environment using blockchain based Hash algorithm and to compare the performance analysis of the hash algorithm against the substitution algorithms.

- i. The first and foremost objective of this study is to identify the security challenges in the cloud environment.
- ii. Designing and developing the computational process for the substitution algorithm and hash algorithm.
- iii. Comparing the performance evaluation of the hash algorithm against other substitutional algorithms in terms of time taken for the execution, amount of memory used and the throughput.

4. Proposed Methodology

Many researchers had contributed their study in the cloud. The flow chart representation of the proposed model to authenticate and protect the cloud data is illustrated in the Fig.2. Initially the user is registered to the cloud service provider through an authenticated server. Then the identification of the user was protected using the substitution algorithm. The user data in the cloud network is protected using the secure hashing algorithm. The change in the hash value is monitored to detect the data damage and data loss to secure the data.

4.1. Substitutional Algorithm

Caesar Cipher Substitution algorithm is considered to be the outstanding substitution algorithm in assuring security to the cloud networks. In this method the secret key is always given in numbers and the decrypted format of the cipher text is saved in the cloud server. This method is considered as a conventional and simplest method of encryption. In this encryption technique the shift method is used for the formation of the cipher text.

In the proposed substitutional technique double encryption of the dataset for the enhanced security is done. In order to generate the cipher text an obsessed numerical value is needed, which is termed as the shift value. Based on the numerical value of the shift the alphabets of the cipher are moved exactly shift times to generate the encrypted text.

The encryption equation based on the given shift is formulated as follows:

$$E_i(x) = (x + i) \bmod 26 \quad (1)$$

Where x represents the alphabetic character in the original data and n refers to the shift. Similarly the decryption equation of the cipher text is given as follows:

$$D_i(x) = (x - i) \bmod 26 \quad (2)$$

Figure 2: Block diagram of the proposed model.

During decryption the alphabets in the cipher text are shifted based on the number of shifts done in the encryption. The steps involved in the double encryption algorithm is explained as follows:

Encryption Algorithm

Step 1: The plain text to be encrypted is obtained from the user.

Step 2: The shift number 1 is given as the secret key 1 to the encryption.

Step 3: The number of shifts based on the secret key 1 is done to generate the cipher text 1.

Step 4: Now for the double encryption secret key 2 is given for the second encryption.

Step 5: Cipher text 1 is shifted based on the secret key 2 to generate the cipher text 2, which is the exact cipher text of the double encryption method.

Decryption Algorithm

Step 1: Two secret keys 1 and 2 with the known cipher rows are given for the decryption.

Step 2: Using secret key 1 first decryption is done and using the secret key 2 second decryption is done.

Step 3: The output of the second decryption is the original data given by the user.

Through the double encryption substitution technique secure user authentication is done with less permutational complexity. This approach produces an output that is impossible to crypt analyse and the method is simple. But the complexity of the proposed substitution-algorithm is higher than the simpler Caesar algorithm with double approach in encryption and decryption. Multiple keys are involved in this procedure which should not be mixed up to produce the original data. In order to ensure the protected authentication in the cloud environment the password of each user is encrypted using the substitutional technique which avoids the storage of the original password in the cloud server.

4.2. HASH ALGORITHM

To protect the data in the cloud server against damage and loss due to malicious attacks and intrusions Hash algorithms are used. In this approach the arbitrary data block of the data set is processed to produce a standard string of the output. With the changes in the hash value damage or data loss can be identified.

There are many secure hashing algorithms which are designed one way to provide strong security. Thus this algorithm is strong enough to detect the intrusion or attack done on the data. This algorithm is combined with the block chain technique which generates the hash value to protect the data. The hashing algorithm used in this model is SHA-512. Hash algorithm is notable for exhibiting overwhelming results. The algorithm works on the basic principle of the simpler modification made in the input block creates a complex impact on the output string and the distant blocks produce a comparable hash value. The hashing of the 512 bit block in the input is formulated as follows:

$$Ha(512) = \sum_{512} p(x)(x \bmod y) (x - i) \quad (3)$$

Where the Ha(512) represents the hash function of the 512 bit block and the p(x) represents parole with mean y. In this algorithm initially the input block is segregated as the fragments with 1024 bits. 64 bit hash value and the rounding constants are generated. This algorithm comprises 80 iterations where the message array is organized as 80 words, each with 64 bits. The iterating loop is scheduled from the 16th bit to 79th bit. The results and performance analysis of the hash algorithm is discussed in the following section.

5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Cloud computing framework is notable for its harmless yield since its implementation in the market. With the advancing approaches and the technical methodologies the security and authentication of the user data and the user is augmented. Thus the added benefits of the advanced cloud computing servers are the perseverance of the user authentication and data confidentiality.

Cloud encryption by Caesar's algorithm provides an encounter model to the mutual and scheduled architecture which is prone to the security breaches. The Caesar's substitution technique used in the proposed model gives more effective security against two attacks namely dictionary attacks and rainbow attacks. These attacks are made to eavesdrop the data exchange, creating a fake browser and stealing the passwords of the users. When the cloud network is in active state, a protocol analyzer is used in the analysis of the activity of the end users. When the user is vulnerable to any attack the admin of the cloud server alerts the users.

As double key is used in the double encryption based Caesar's cipher method enhanced security is achieved. The processing speed is fast as the technique is not computationally complex, also requires less time to encrypt and decrypt making this as the time consuming algorithm. As the data size of the encrypted cipher is same as that of the original message, lesser storage space is required when compared with the other substitutional techniques. The key exchange process in this technique is simpler without any challenging issues.

The Hash algorithm 512 encryption is used in the cloud server to protect the data. In this model the user data is hashed by the string of hash values. Variance in these values detects the modification or loss of user data and alerts the user for the same. The Hash 512 algorithm proposed in this model highly contributes to the fake browser problems which detects the attacks in the early stage and prevents them. The output parameters of the single key Caesar model, SHA 512 model and the proposed model are compared in Table 2.

5.1. Execution Time:

A process is defined as the end user application running at the user system which comprises single or multiple executions. The average time taken for the execution of a single process and the amount of energy spent on the execution of the process is calculated to find its efficiency. In the proposed model 1813 kbps of execution speed and 5813 kbps of the application running speed is obtained making it more efficient than the individual models.

5.2. Throughput:

Throughput is the measure of the productivity of the processors responding to any algorithm. It is measured

as the amount of data exchanged between the users. The throughput of the file uploading process should be high enough to upload all the data and the throughput of the usage should be small enough to be computationally simple and fast. The proposed model exhibits highest throughput for file upload and lowest for the application usage.

5.3. Memory Utilization:

This denotes the amount of field taken by the respective algorithms to complete their processes.

Table 2: Output attribute comparison

Output Parameters	Caeser's model	SHA 512 model	Proposed model
Execution speed (kbps)	322	1743	1813.45
Application running speed (kbps)	580	632	5813
Throughput (file upload) (kbps)	150	157	194
Throughput (Application Usage)(kbps)	75	62	45
Memory Utilization (kbps)	240	225	180

In comparison with the other model the proposed model take only 180 kbps to complete the execution of the process making this encryption model more effective and rapid enough

6. CONCLUSION

In the communication era huge data are being transacted through cloud servers. All these transactions are demanded to be secure and perfect. To ensure this data security and confidentiality certain security algorithms were developed. In this series, a hybrid algorithm comprising of double encrypting substitutional approach and Hash algorithm is implemented. This algorithm is proved to be more efficient in providing data security and data confidentiality in effective way than the existing algorithms. This algorithm is implemented to prove to overcome the security limitations in the cloud network by suppressing the risks like unauthorized data access, data damage, data theft and data leaks. Thus this study has achieved all the objectives outlined and the comparative analysis done with the existing algorithms proves the same.

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<p>FORM 2 THE PATENTS ACT, 1970 (39 of 1970) & The Patent Rules, 2003 COMPLETE SPECIFICATION (See sections 10 & rule 13)</p>		
<p>TITLE OF THE INVENTION – A SYSTEM AND METHOD FOR SECURED ARCHITECTURE WITH EFFECTIVE DATA SHARING IN CLOUD BASED BIG DATA STORAGE ENVIRONMENT</p>		
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<p>COMPLETE SPECIFICATION</p> <p>The following specification particularly describes the invention and the manner in which it is to be performed</p>		

FIELD OF INVENTION

[01] The present invention relates to the big data security of the cloud environment in multiple layers. More particularly, A hybrid algorithmic module was developed for the important procedures
5 like Data compression, Data clustering and Data Indexing. Corresponding attributes were tested for the analysis of the performance metrics. Though many research and studies were done on the cloud security none of them proved the strength and effectiveness of the security architecture.

10

BACKGROUND OF INVENTION

[02] Background description includes information that may be useful in understanding the present invention. It is not an admission that any of the information provided herein is prior art or relevant to
15 the presently claimed invention, or that any publication specifically or implicitly referenced is prior art.

[03] One of the main challenges for providing Big Data Analytics-as-a-Service in the public Cloud is security of the enterprise data that
20 is transferred and stored in the public cloud storage facilities and used for further analytics processing using Big Data platforms

such as Hadoop®. This is due to the fact that while the enterprise data storage environment can be trusted for storing sensitive enterprise data, once this data is transferred to the cloud it is exposed to the system administrators of the public cloud service provider that can access the data at any time. While the data can be secured before being uploaded to the public cloud, this complicates further analytics processing that the data might undergo in the cloud using Analytics-as-a-Service since analytics algorithms running on the Hadoop® platform cannot process encrypted/secured data. We note that such Analytics-as-a-Service can involve the deployment and provisioning of analytics processing platforms such as Hadoop® on physical/virtual machines in the cloud.

[004]5 Distributed storage has brought better approaches for putting away, recovering, and sharing computerized information, transforming the possibility of on-demand information sharing into the real world. In any case, simple and quick availability is periodically an equivalent word of security weakness when it goes to the sharing of delicate information [(Huang et al. 2015)] The information security and protection has become a basic issue that confines many cloud applications. One of the significant worries in

security and protection is brought about by the way that cloud administrators have opportunities to reach the delicate information. This worry drastically expands clients' tension and lessens the adoptability of distributed computing in numerous 5 fields, for example, the financial business and administrative organizations such as governments.

[05] The traditional model of Big Data doesn't indicate any level for catching the sensitivity of both structured and unstructured data. 10 It also needs to merge the idea of insurance and security where the threat of revealing individual information is likely restricted. Given the high volume of tremendous data, and the mix of structured and unstructured information requires some arrangement of new models for Big Data in order to expand 15 protection and security. Security in Big data is an emerging topic which is considerable interest among researchers since the deployment of Big data storage systems is a valuable target by intruders [(Santos and Masala 2019)], [(Jong and Shin 2016)]. Big Data is defined as the 3V's of information such as high volume, 20 high velocity and high variety of information. Some of the application of Big data are given in paper [(Bronson, K., & Keevil 2016)], [(Bhola 2015)], and [(Bearman 2015)]. With the use of

huge volume of data, Big data storage systems lead to big complexity and also security breaches occur, which is difficult to solve in the real-world environment [(Mesh ram et al. 2019)]. However, Cloud server or any Big data server is not trustworthy.

5

[06] Embodiments relate generally to methods and systems for data sharing. One embodiment relates generally to a method for encrypting data using a sharable file-level key. The sharable file-level key allows for sharing of individual files that are protected by
10 a workgroup key without exposing the workgroup key to entities outside of the workgroup. The sharable file-level key may be generated using a workgroup key associated with the file and unique information associated with the file.

[007]5 Another embodiment relates generally to securing data across a network, wherein a portion of the network is public and a portion of the network is private. In some embodiments, the data is encrypted and split. A computing image is generated and distributed across the network. This computing image may include
20 preloaded files that provide pointers to the data that was encrypted and split. No access or replication of the data on the public portion of the network is needed in order for a user of the

private portion of the network to access the data from the public portion of the network.

[08] Current solutions to this problem either: (approach a) assume that the enterprise fully trusts the public cloud service provider to not access its data once the data is uploaded there in clear text, which might not be acceptable if the data is sensitive (e.g., due to regulatory and/or legal reasons and/or so forth); or (approach b) attempt to fully encrypt the underlying file system of the physical/virtual machines onto which the Big Data platform is deployed. The latter approach (approach b) has certain drawbacks, including: (1) inflexible separation between secured and unsecured enterprise data that might be needed for analytics processing, which lacks fine-grained control over which files are secured and which are not secured; (2) requiring configuration changes of the underlying operating system onto which the Big Data analytics platform is deployed, which might create additional administrative and management costs for the public cloud service provider; and (3) not allowing for fine-grain control over the security algorithms and parameters used on a per data file basis.

[09] The former approach (approach a) has certain drawbacks, including: (1) non-compliance with regulatory requirements (e.g., Federal Financial Institutions Examination Council (FFIEC), Health Insurance Portability and Accountability Act (HIPPA), etc.) that might dictate that certain data of sensitive nature (e.g., financial records, health records, etc.) cannot be stored in clear-text in public service cloud providers; (2) public cloud service providers may have to respond to government subpoenas and other legal actions that could force them to hand over data to authorities that the original owner of the data might not want to reveal (e.g., a company based out of one jurisdiction such as Germany might not want to hand over sensitive data to the U.S. entities if the cloud service provider is based out of the U.S.); (3) it is not always possible to guarantee safeguards on data that resides with public cloud service providers, in order to consequently trust that the enterprise data will be handled with all appropriate care and procedures that the enterprise itself follows.

[0010] Thus, there is a need for A special authentication protocol was proposed for this architecture, Big data security is a challenging task with many complexities. Big data security is mainly

dependent on the infrastructure, data type, management, resource allocation and management and Data analysis.

[0011] Further limitations and disadvantages of conventional approaches will become apparent to one of skill in the art through comparison of described systems with some aspects of the present disclosure, as outlined in the remainder of the present application and concerning the drawings.

[0012] As used in the description herein and throughout the claims that follow, the meaning of "a," "an," and "the" includes plural reference unless the context dictates otherwise. Also, as used in the description herein, the meaning of "in" includes "in" and "on" unless the context dictates otherwise.

15

[0013] Groupings of alternative elements or embodiments of the invention disclosed herein are not to be construed as limitations.

Each group member can be referred to and claimed individually or in any or a combination with other members of the group or other elements found herein. One or more members of a group can be included in, or deleted from, a group for reasons of convenience and/or patentability. When any such inclusion or deletion occurs,

the specification is herein deemed to contain the group as modified thus fulfilling the written description of all groups used in the appended claims.

SUMMARY OF INVENTION

[00145] The present invention relates to the big data security of the cloud environment in multiple layers. More particularly, A hybrid algorithmic module was developed for the important procedures like Data compression, Data clustering and Data Indexing. Corresponding attributes were tested for the analysis of the
10 performance metrics. Though many research and studies were done on the cloud security none of them proved the strength and effectiveness of the security architecture.

[0015] Big data security is a challenging task with many complexities. Big
15 data security is mainly dependent on the infrastructure, data type, management, resource allocation and management and Data analysis. Cloud computing is the trending technology dealing with the big data analysis and storage. A novel architecture involving the data outsourcing, data sharing and data management is
20 proposed for the security of the cloud environment in multiple layers.
A hybrid algorithmic module was developed for the

important procedures like Data compression, Data clustering and Data Indexing. Corresponding attributes were tested for the analysis of the performance metrics. Though many research and studies were done on the cloud security none of them proved the strength and effectiveness of the security architecture. Hence a decentralized security architecture based on the block chain codes was developed for the IoT applications. A special authentication protocol was proposed for this architecture. All these experiments were conducted in a spark environment to demonstrate the effectiveness of the security performance against space complexity, time complexity and throughput.

[0016] Our proposed work comprised of four entities including Trusted Center (TC), Data Owner (DO), Data User (DU) and Cloud Server (CS). Usage of each component is described in the following: (1) TC: It is a trusted, robust, rich storage space, and a powerful entity created for security purpose. It is used to register data users and data owners and make secure communication between either DO and CS or DU and CS. It has access to bootstrap the entire security system employed in CS. It maintains the secret key for all data owners and users and revokes based on their past and current behaviors. (2) DO: DO is register into TC and thus

authorized DO can send their data for stored into Cloud. DO upload files into CS by mainly three steps: data-sensitive level assessment, compression and encryption. (3) DU: DU is registered into TC so those valid users can access the files stored into CS. For data decryption, DU requests a key from TC and then decrypt it. So that users who have the secret key have the right for data access. (4) CS: It consists of files sent by DO. It performs several operations such as data storage, retrieval, management and access control. It provides several supports for DO such as ciphertext update, modifies the ciphertext, and deletes the file from CS. To store data in a Cloud, DO requests secret key from TC. According to user credentials, TC registers DO and issue secretkey. Then the data compressed and then encrypted with the use of secret key and stores the encrypted data to the Cloud. DU can request CS for data access. They verified DU identity using TC and then key is issued for decryption. To manage 3V's of Big data, we deployed HDFS into Cloud environment, which provides sufficient storage space and access control for both data owners and users.

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[0017] According to an aspect of the present principles, a method is provided. The method includes reading a secure file, by a Secure

Distributed File System in a public cloud service provider having a processor and a memory device. The reading step includes computing a hash of a name of the secure file to obtain a hashed file name. The reading step further includes finding metadata for the secure file using the hashed file name. The reading step also includes retrieving a sharing policy identifier from the metadata. The reading step additionally includes obtaining authorization from an external entity to decrypt the secure file. The reading step further includes extracting a security key and encrypted data file names from the metadata using the sharing policy identifier. The reading step also includes requesting one or more encrypted data files that form the secure file from a node of the public cloud service provider. The reading step additionally includes at least one of decrypting and reconstructing plaintext data for the secure file from the one or more encrypted data files.

[0018] Further limitations and disadvantages of conventional approaches will become apparent to one of skill in the art through comparison of described systems with some aspects of the present disclosure, as outlined in the remainder of the present application and concerning the drawings.

BRIEF DESCRIPTION OF THE DRAWINGS

[0019] FIG. 1 illustrates the working principle involved in the invention.

DETAILED DESCRIPTION

[00205] The following is a detailed description of embodiments of the disclosure depicted in the accompanying drawings. The embodiments are in such detail as to communicate the disclosure. However, the amount of detail offered is not intended to limit the anticipated variations of embodiments; on the contrary, the intention is to cover all modifications, equivalents, and alternatives falling within the spirit and scope of the present disclosure as defined by the appended claims.

[0021] Embodiments of the present invention include various steps, which will be described below. The steps may be performed by hardware components or may be embodied in machine-executable instructions, which may be used to cause a general-purpose or special-purpose processor programmed with the instructions to perform the steps. Alternatively, steps may be performed by a combination of hardware, software, and firmware and/or by human operators.

[0022] Furthermore, embodiments may be implemented by hardware, software, firmware, middleware, microcode, hardware description languages, or any combination thereof. When implemented in software, firmware, middleware, or microcode, the program code or code segments to perform the necessary tasks (e.g., a computer program product) may be stored in a machine-readable medium.

[0023] Various terms as used herein are shown below. To the extent a term used in a claim is not defined below, it should be given the broadest definition persons in the pertinent art have given that term as reflected in printed publications and issued patents at the time of filings.

[0024] Fig 1 depicts the Big data-enabled Cloud environment for data owners and users, which serves for different applications and services. The Data Owners is often referring to as to assign responsibility and accountability for specific data or refers to concepts such as assurance of data quality and security. The data of the Data Owners are stored in Cloud which is the efficient and easy way of storing Big data. Data Users are the individual who uses the data as part of their job. Application and services can be of any type such as Healthcare, Industry, Energy Management, Renewable Energy Sources, Building Management, and so on.

Figure.1. Big Data Enabled Cloud Environment In view of our perception, we need to unfortunately call attention to that none of the as of now existing encryption methods gives appropriate security insurance, and all the systems share a similar issue of having a high calculation cost. Our principal responsibility here, in this manner, is to offer a provably secure encryption system with a low calculation cost. The significant contribution of the paper is toward proposing a novel approach called Secure Authentication and Data Sharing in Cloud (SADS-Cloud) enabled Big Data Environment.

[0025] While the foregoing describes various embodiments of the invention, other and further embodiments of the invention may be devised without departing from the basic scope thereof. The scope of the invention is determined by the claims that follow. The invention is not limited to the described embodiments, versions, or examples, which are included to enable a person having ordinary skill in the art to make and use the invention when combined with information and knowledge available to the person.

We claim:

1. A system for secured architecture with effective data sharing in cloud based big data storage environment comprising:
 - 5 Trusted Center (TC) Module;
Data Owner (DO) Module;
Data User (DU) Module; and
Cloud Server (CS) Module;
 - wherein the TC Module is used to register data users and
10 data owners and make secure communication between
either DO and CS or DU and CS;
 - wherein the TC Module has access to bootstrap the entire
security system employed in CS;
 - wherein the TC Module maintains the secret key for all data
15 owners and users and revokes based on their past and
current behaviors;
 - wherein Data Owner (DO) Module is register into TC and
authorized DO can send their data for stored into Cloud.
- 20 2. The system as claimed in claim 1, wherein DO Module upload
files into CS by three steps: data-sensitive level assessment,
compression and encryption.

3. The system as claimed in claim 1, wherein DU Module is registered into TC so those valid users can access the files stored into CS wherein for data decryption, DU requests a
5 key from TC and then decrypt it.

4. The system as claimed in claim 1, wherein CS Module consists of files sent by DO and performs several operations including data storage, retrieval, management and access
10 control.

5. The system as claimed in claim 1, wherein a hybrid algorithmic module was implemented for the important procedures including Data compression, Data clustering and
15 Data Indexing wherein corresponding attributes are tested for the analysis of the performance metrics.

6. The system as claimed in claim 1, wherein wherein the architecture involving a decentralized security architecture
20 based on the block chain codes is used for the IoT applications and a special authentication protocol is used for this architecture.

7. A method for secured architecture with effective data sharing in cloud based big data storage environment wherein the method includes reading a secure file by a Secure Distributed File System in a public cloud service provider having a processor and a memory device.

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ABSTRACT

A SYSTEM AND METHOD FOR SECURED ARCHITECTURE WITH EFFECTIVE DATA SHARING IN CLOUD BASED BIG DATA STORAGE ENVIRONMENT

5 The invention disclosed a system and method for secured architecture with effective data scaring in cloud based big data storage environment. A novel architecture involving the data outsourcing, data sharing and data management is proposed for the security of the cloud environment in multiple layers. A hybrid
10 algorithmic module has been developed for the important procedures like Data compression, Data clustering and Data Indexing. Corresponding attributes are tested for the analysis of the performance metrics. Though many research and studies weredone on the cloud security none of them proved the strength and
15 effectiveness of the security architecture. Hence, a decentralized security architecture based on the block chain codes is developed for the IoT applications. A special authentication protocol is proposed for this architecture. All these experiments are conducted in a spark environment to demonstrate the
20 effectiveness of the security performance against space complexity, time complexity and throughput.

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FIG. 1 illustrates the working principle involved in the invention.

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CONCLUSION

The communication era involves the transmission of vast amounts of data through cloud servers. The demand for secure and flawless transactions is essential. Certain security algorithms were developed to ensure data security and confidentiality. The series implements a hybrid algorithm that combines a double encrypting substitutional approach and Hash algorithm. The efficiency of this algorithm in ensuring data security and confidentiality surpasses that of existing algorithms. The implementation of this algorithm aims to address security limitations in cloud networks by mitigating risks such as unauthorized data access, data damage, data theft, and data leaks. A unique framework was designed for block chain networks hosted on cloud servers, which utilizes the elliptical curve encryption algorithm and the Honey encryption algorithm to protect the user's identity and transactions. The computational time and cost support the suggested model's performance indicators.